

EVOLVEMENT OF ECOTOURISM TO BUILD DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES IN THE VOLGA-VIATKA DISTRICT

DESARROLLO DEL ECOTURISMO PARA CONSTRUIR ESTRATEGIAS DE DESARROLLO EN EL DISTRIOTVOLGA-VYATKA

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RESUMEN

Este documento llevó a cabo un análisis FODA sobre el desarrollo del ecoturismo para desarrollar estrategias de desarrollo en el distrito económico de Volga-Vyatka y luego propuso estrategias de desarrollo. Nuestro hallazgo muestra que las estrategias de desarrollo ecoturístico de Volga-Vyatka fueron: mejorar la conciencia ecológica de toda la población y crear un buen ambiente para el desarrollo del ecoturismo; romper el cuello de botella del talento del desarrollo del ecoturismo mediante una lluvia de ideas sobre un producto turístico, hacer un plan maestro científico y viable para el desarrollo del ecoturismo en Kotelnich; desarrollar productos de ecoturismo de calidad; estrategias de marketing innovadoras para el ecoturismo.

Palabras clave: ecoturismo, método FODA, protección de la naturaleza, dinosaurios at Kotelnich

ABSTRACT

This paper carried out a SWOT analysis on ecotourism development to build development strategies in the Volga-Vyatka economic district, and then proposed development strategies. Our finding shows that Volga-Vyatka Ecotourist development strategies were: enhance the ecological awareness of the entire population and create a good atmosphere for ecotourism development; break the talent bottleneck of ecotourism development by brainstorming a tourism product, make a scientific and feasible master plan for the ecotourism development of Kotelnich; develop quality ecotourism products; innovate marketing strategies for ecotourism.

Keywords: ecotourism, SWOT method, nature protection, dinosaurs at Kotelnich.

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INTRODUCTION

In connection with the ecological situation of our time, ecotourism (ECOT) is becoming truly relevant. To date, according to some indicators, ECOT accounts for 20% of the world tourism market (United Nations World Tourism Organization, 2016). The chosen theme is relevant because ecological tourism is a popular area in the tourist industry, which goal is harmonious existence with nature, as well as a careful attitude to natural, cultural and historical monuments (Stronza, 2007).

With new border policies and the development of travel infrastructure, international tourism to Russia experienced double-digit growth in the past few years. Yet, few authors have reported on the challenges the country faces towards sustainable tourism development and competitiveness.

This paper carried out a SWOT analysis on ecotourism development inside Kotelnichsky district - Kirovsky oblast, and then proposed development strategies; in other words, this analysis discusses issues that have affected and that will continue to affect tourism in Russia.

In this model, the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and strategies of ecotourism in the Kotelnichsky region has been investigated. Kirov Oblast has a good potential in the development of ecological tourism, since there is a large number of untouched natural areas in it. The Kirov region is included in federal interregional routes and in the given region development of cultural-cognitive, sanatorium-resort, rural events, fishing and hunting tourism is observed (Zarubina, 2017).

These attractions are because of the geographical location and historical and natural resources of the Kirov Oblast, which combine a pleasant climate and the picturesque nature of the Vyatka landscape.

The status of Kotelnichsky district is increasingly important, so the analysis of it is not only needed for summarization and further development of the Kotelnich ECOT, but also an inevitable path for eco-regional development policies.

SWOT Analysis of Ecotourism Development

Kotelnichsky district occupies the western part of the Kirov Oblast; it has a length of 100 km from North to South and 70 km from West to East. Due to its geographical location, forests occupy about 50% of the territory and consist mainly of spruce and fir. There is still an abundance of strawberries, blueberries, raspberries and cranberries (Smolentseva, 2014).

The two main fluvial arteries are the Vyatka and Moloma rivers. Both are flat and possess a large number of old lakes in the floodplains of their valleys. In addition,

there are about 50 smaller rivers and streams. The rivers Vyatka and Moloma are rich in fish.

In the Kotelnich district there are such natural monuments as: the largest site of the Pareiasaurus, the Nurgush Nature Reserve, the northernmost Oak Grove, and the Coastal landslide.

A huge number of ecological places create an excellent opportunity for the creation and development of ECOT. Residents of the district prefer outdoor recreation, which means an increase in demand for natural tourism. The forest is the main wealth of the region. An oak grove with a total of 1540 hectares and protected by the state occupies an exceptional importance for the preservation of nature. On its territory the following lakes and old towns are located: Dubovoye, Buldakovo and Staritsa.

The next unique subject is Nurgush Reserve. The reserve is famous for its extraordinary natural diversity: it has 50 lakes and 5 rivers, 550 plant species, 87 moss species, 94 lichen species, 11 algae species (Konishev, 2017).

Ecological tourism is allowed in the reserve, we can find from moose, wild boars and otters. Also, is possible to observe rare animals like Russian muskrat and also birds as whitetail and osprey, listed in the Red Book.

The main feature is the Skornyakovo ancient settlement. On the right bank of Vyatka for 25 km extends the largest archaeological site of terrestrial vertebrates that lived on Earth 240 million years ago. The brand of kotelnich eskikhpareyazavrov is known far beyond the Kirov region. All paleontologists' institutions of the world know about this land as a unique phenomenon: in 20 years of work of scientists at the Kotelnichsky locality, have discovered about 20 unknown animals of the Permian period. Previously, this place was an ancient river. On the shore, where excavations are carried out, a large number of reptile bones have been preserved, which are now being worked on (Shebtsov, 2014).

Four kilometers from Kotelnich is the Coastal landslide, which is a striking example of geological strata. Down the river, for 50 meters, there was a shift of the whole section of the spruce forest, while the flora remained unscathed.

Finally, this research titled "evolution of ecotourism to build development strategies in the Volga-Vyatka district" aims to carry out a SWOT analysis on ecotourism development to build development strategies in the Volga-Vyatka economic district.

METHODOLOGY

This research has been done by SWOT analysis; we coded strengths, weaknesses and opportunities according to the coefficients of our survey in the group site *Kotelnich people* in Vkontakte and literature review (Bautista, 2017).

The following steps are taken to determine the SWOT model:

First step: Identifying the internal and external factors effective in the ecotourism of the Kotelnichsky region,

Second step: Determining the weight of internal and external factors effective in ecotourism of the Kotelnichsky area,

Third step: Establishing a matrix for assessing internal and external factors effective in ecotourism in the Kotelnichsky area,

Fourth step: Designing a SWOT Matrix

To implement the model, the brain storming method was used; in this method a group of experts in the field of ecotourism in the Kotelnichsky region was gathered, and each of them was asked to express as much as possible the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and strategies of ecotourism in the Kotelnichsky region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Kotelnich SWOT analysis demonstrates that ECOT development (Table 1) has significance to the sustainable development of its tourism industry, and of course help us to identify advantages and disadvantages.

Table 1. SWOT Analysis of Kotelnich

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rich natural and archaeological resources. 2. Beautiful scenery and vast forest. 3. Abundant cultural resources. 4. Growing popularity of ecotourism. 5. Low cost for energy and water consumption. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tourism flow is limited to local residents of nearby settlements. 2. Far from the airport and railway stations. 3. Low professional quality of ecotourism practitioners. 4. Low-investment business ideas in the region 5. Lack of depth in ecotourism development.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Become the most important Dinosaur Park in Russia 2. Become a UNESCO World Heritage because of Dinosaur Kotelnich park. 3. Incentives to protect rare species and unique ecosystems. 3. Attracting more profit from tourism. 4. Low risk investments with the highest returns 5. Reduce poverty by ecotourism. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Deterioration of the environment 2. Unfavorable economic situation in the region

By: Tregubova, Zinovyeva and Bautista (2018)

Ecotourism Development Strategies

By brain storming we can put in order all of this idea, to then establish comprehensive mechanisms and development strategies. In the vast majority of ECOT development zones in Kotelnich, the demand for basic necessities, food and clothing, has not been completely met. In order to solve this problem, there is a risk of damaging the ecological environment to meet these needs. Therefore, we should vigorously develop the economy, and raise it to a higher level, fulfill the demand of the people for basic needs, and promote the demand for ECOT development.

Improving the Ecological Popularization

First, we must stretch the time threshold of ecological education, starting from the pre-school stage through primary, junior high, high school and university stages. Second, we must avoid homogeneous eco-education. We must teach students in accordance to their aptitudes and teach them in due time, customizing ecological education to meet the physical and psychological characteristics of students of different learning stages. In pre-school stage, ecological introduction is needed to

be given; while in primary school stage, basic eco-knowledge is to be learnt. During the junior high and high school stages, ecological education should be carried out. And comprehensive practical ecological education should be conducted, with the integration of theory and practice, during the university stage. Finally, a batch of highly qualified ecological teachers should be trained.

The key of the national ecological education system are the teachers; whose ecological literacy has a direct impact on the effectiveness of ecological education. Therefore, it is necessary to implement the strategy of “going out and introducing”, sending teachers to participate in training and inviting ecological experts to give lectures. Scientific research should be promoted to improve the quality of teaching. We should encourage teachers to engage in scientific research on ecology and help them broaden their horizons and accumulate knowledge of ecological theory and practice. Accelerate the integration of new and old media, and innovate the popularizing idea of ecological civilization. When using traditional media such as distributing leaflets, holding lectures, and pulling banners, it is even more important to promote online knowledge of ecological civilization with the help of Vkontakte, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter and online live broadcast platforms.

Brainstorming a Touristic Product

Ecotourism is the advanced stage of tourism development. The development of ECOT needs multi-participation and multi-disciplinary cooperation. Talents are the key factors affecting the development of ECOT. With the guidance of Brainstorming, Kotelnich should establish a comprehensive mechanism of attracting and using talents. We can introduce talents at different levels and provide them with relevant fiscal incentives and life guarantees. Only in this way it will be possible to retain talents and provide intellectual support for ECOT development. Therefore, the Kotelnich Tourism Administration should establish collaboration mechanisms with different universities, attracting excellent Tourism teachers and outstanding graduates to join in Kotelnich ECOT development.

Making a Master Plan of Ecotourism Development

Kotelnich can establish ECOT big data, create smart ECOT and realize the “innovative” development of ECOT. The development of ECOT is a systematic project that requires multiple collaborations. Adhering to the concept of coordination can we unite all forces and gather all the resources possible to form a joint force for the development of ECOT. The ecological environment is a large system and it maintains a dynamic balance through mutual interaction between different regions. In the process of ECOT development, we should respect the natural laws of the ecosystem and guide the development of ECOT with the concept of openness, sharing, and greenness to ensure the balance of regional eco-environment.

Setting up an Overall Planning Team for Ecotourism Development

The formation of a team is neither a simple patchwork of talents, nor pure introduction of an outside team. To establish a scientific team, we should pay attention to the following aspects:

Team members should consist both of local tourism management talents and introduced tourism experts. Local tourism management experts are well aware of the situation of Kotelnich ECOT development, ensuring that the plan made is in accordance with the local condition, while introduced professionals in tourism development can bring fresh ideas to the team, help team members broaden their horizons and eliminate limitations of planning by standing at a new height. ECOT development is a comprehensive discipline that involves many disciplines and requires the collaboration of professionals in various fields. A reasonable team should be composed of tourism management talents with the knowledge of professional planning, aesthetic talented artists, literary talents creative in culture, historical experts who will tap into cultural heritage, and computer talents who can use the new media and technology. We can say that the preparation of planning is not only an intellectual activity but also a physical work.

Developing Quality Ecotourism Products

Lu Hongsheng's research (2004) on the type of ECOT, considered the specific conditions of one region in China as a model of development, the analysis compares the features of existing scenic spots (Hongsheng, 2004). It finds that the ECOT can be divided into 8 types, including river rafting ECOT, geographic landscape ECOT, rural ECOT, modern agricultural ECOT, historical cultural ECOT, religious cultural eco-tourism, red ECOT and forest ECOT. Considering the characteristics of tourism resources and regional characteristics, it is believed that they all have tourism functions and other functions, respectively, drifting expeditions, scientific research, rest, agricultural experience, scientific research, moralization, education, and rehabilitation.

Market Positioning

According to the law of distance attenuation, the primary ECOT source markets are Kirov, Sharya and Yoshkar-Ola. These cities are important sources of tourists for Kotelnich due to easy access to transportation and low travel cost. Moscow, Kazan and other major capital cities with a relatively high level of economic development, are ideal secondary source markets for Kotelnich, and therefore, should be actively explored. Overseas countries are the three-level source markets for Kotelnich's ECOT, which should be actively pursued after the successful building of Kotelnich ECOT brand.

Image Positioning of Ecotourism

Based on the SWOT analysis, functional positioning and market positioning of

ECOT, it is found that ECOT in Kotelnich has two major features. First, there are up to five ECOT scenic spots with large-scale clusters and broad development prospects. Second, its ECOT has a monopolistic competitiveness owing to the paleontological evidence and the reputation. Based on these two characteristics, the image of Kotelnich's ECOT is positioned as a blessed land, and a destination to mental relax and physical health.

Development of Quality Ecotourism Products

It is mandatory to promote infrastructure, improve service facilities, build well-connected transportation and create a favorable ecological environment. We propose to establish one 5-A tourist attraction, two 4-A tourist attractions, one national ECOT demonstration zone, one regional tourism demonstration zones by 2025.

Innovating Marketing Strategies for Ecotourism

New media platform for ECOT marketing can be actively promoted in traditional websites, printed media and marketing boards. ECOT activities can also be broadcasted online through radio, local TV and other platforms, or live VK-Facebook broadcasters can be used to expand the influence. Old and new media will ensure simultaneous online and offline interactions.

Game Marketing Pattern

Game players can get travel coupons after striking down the beast in the virtual Kotelnich sceneries. Besides coupons, game players will also have a better understanding of the region. While traveling, the people with tourism coupons will get online game coupons, which later can be used for online games again. This is a win-win cooperation for both game developers and the region administration.

Social Networking Marketing Pattern

ECOT marketing agencies should apply for instant messaging tools such as Instagram, Facebook and V Kontakte, and use administrative tools to obtain high-level access to software. Also, the ECOT marketing section can be set up in major online forums, where the exquisite graphic, textual, and audio information of ECOT can be uploaded to form a good ECOT marketing atmosphere (Bautista,2017; Cheng, 2013).

Marketing Pattern

We recommend to build a marketing platform, establish a marketing website, and achieve independent e-commerce (Tiberghien, Garkavenko and Ashirbekova, 2013). It is important to contact and make cooperation with TripAdvisor, Airbnb, booking and other popular brands. Finally, we suggest establish official flagship store of Kotelnich ECOT to sell tickets and travel support services, and accept tourist request (Bautista, 2017).

CONCLUSIONS

Developing of Kotelnich ecotourism is possible, our analysis shows the strengths and opportunities to build a plan for the Revitalization and Development of this place and directly improve the conditions of Oblast Kirov. Therefore, it has great strategic significances for the national ECOT development. However, due to the constraints of natural, economic and social conditions, the ECOT development still has a long way to go. It is urgently necessary for the central government to give preferential policies, the local government to increase investment, and the multidisciplinary experts' groups to participate.

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